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The Oral Tradition Of Rāga Rāmakalī In South Indian And North Indian Music

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Abstract

Dēśīya is seen for the first time in the first quarter of 18th century in the text “Rāgalakṣaṇam” (RL-MV) of Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī. Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī classifies 25 rāga-s under dēśīya classification. Following RL-MV, Subbarāma Dīkṣitar in his work “Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini (SSP), 1904 AD, classifies 23 rāga-s as dēśīya rāga-s. Subbarāma Dīkṣitar also mentions that the dēśīya rāga-s are auttara rāga-s which have come from the Northern region. Before Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī’s RL-MV, the term dēśī is seen in “Rāgalakṣaṇamu” (RL-S) of Śāhaji, 1684-1711 AD. He does not mention the reason for such a classification and mentions 16 rāga-s under the dēśī classification.

RL-S and SSP mention 3 rāga-s, (Jana) tōḍi, Pūrvi and Māruva in common. Apart from these 3 rāga-s, one rāga Rāmakalī has been mentioned as dēśīya in SSP. Subbarāma Dīkṣitar gives a note that it is called by people from other regions (auttara rāga) as “Bibhās”, while explaining the rāga Rāmakalī. Śāhaji mentions the rāga Bibhāsu as a dēśī rāga. Interestingly, Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī in his text mentions both Rāmakalī and Bibhāsu under the dēśīya classification but describes only Rāmakalī. Hence, it is imperative to look into the Hindustāni counterparts as well.

Though there are textual references to the rāga, the rāga can be well understood only with the existing oral tradition. Hence this paper focuses on the oral tradition of the rāga Rāmakalī in South Indian and North Indian Music. Since, Subbarāma Dīkṣitar mentions that rāga Rāmakalī is also called as Bibhās and incidentally, Bibhās has been mentioned by Śāhaji under dēśī classification, it becomes imperative to look into the oral tradition of rāga Bibhās also.

Keywords: Rāga-s, dēśīya, dēśī, oral tradition, South Indian Music, North Indian Music, rāga Rāmakali, rāga Bibhās, Historical reference.

1. Introduction:

Dēśīya is seen mentioned for the first time in “Rāgalakṣaṇam” (RL-MV) of Muḍdu Vēnkaṭamakhī, where he classifies 25 rāga-s as dēśīya rāga-s. “Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarśini (SSP), 1904 AD of Subbarāma Dīkṣitar classifies 23 rāga-s as dēśīya rāga-s. Before Muḍdu Vēnkaṭamakhī’s RL-MV, the term dēśī is seen in “Rāgalakṣaṇamu” (RL-S) of Śāhaji, 1684-1711 AD and he mentions 16 dēśī rāga-s. Here, the term dēśī is considered to be dēśīya according to Muḍdu Vēnkaṭamakhī and Subbarāma Dīkṣitar.

The rāga Rāmakali has been mentioned to be a dēśīya rāga according to Subbarāma Dīkṣitar and he gives a note that it is called by people from other regions (auttara rāga) as “Bibhās”, while explaining the rāga. Śāhaji mentions the rāga Bibhāsu as a dēśī rāga. Muḍdu Vēnkaṭamakhī in his text mentions both Rāmakalī and Bibhāsu under the dēśīya classification but describes only Rāmakali.

There are many textual references to the rāga. But only with the existing oral tradition, the rāga can be well understood. Hence this presentation focuses on the oral tradition of the rāga Rāmakali in South Indian and North Indian Music.

The rāga Rāmakali in South Indian Music is not very popular. There is only one composition which has been documented and is seen in oral practice. The rāga is called as Rāmkali in North Indian Music and is popular. There are many compositions in Hindustāni Music in the rāga. Since the rāga-s existence is traced back to 4 centuries, it is important to get an overview of the textual tradition with respect to the rāga.

2. An overview of the textual references to Rāmakali:

2.1 Rāmakalī is mentioned in the following texts:

1. Rāgamañjarī (RM) of Paṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1572-1578 AD)
2. Hṛdayaprakāśa (HP) of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 AD)
3. Anūpasanḡitaratnākara (ASR) of Bhāvabhaṭṭa (17th-18th C.AD)
4. RL-MV
5. Rāgalakṣaṇa (RL) 18th – 19th C.AD
6. SSP

These texts mention Rāmakalī under the 15th mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme of Caturdanḍīprakāśikā. All the texts mention ‘sa’ as the graha, amśa and nyāsa svāra. Apart from Rāmakali, there are two other rāga-s which have similar nomenclature. They are named Rāmakrī and Rāmakarī.

2.2 Rāmakrī is seen mentioned in the following texts:

1. Sadrāgacandrōdaya (SRC) of Paṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1583-1589 AD)
2. Rāgamāla (RMala) of Paṇḍarīkaviṭṭhala (1576 AD)
3. Rāgavibodha (RV) of Sōmanātha (1609 AD)

These texts mention Rāmakrī under the 15th mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme of Caturdanḍīprakāśikā. All the texts mention ‘sa’ as the graha, amśa and nyāsa svāra.

2.3 Rāmakarī is seen mentioned in the following texts:

1. Saṅgīta Pārijāta (SP) of Ahōbala (17th C.AD)

2. Rāgatattvavibōdha (RTV) of Śrīnīvāsa (after 1650 AD)
3. Hṛdayakautuka (HK) of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 AD)

Rāmakarī mentioned in SP and RTV possess tīvratara ma and the mēla of Rāmakarī corresponds to the 51st mēla of the 72 mēla scheme. HK mentions Rāmakarī under Gaurī Samasthān which corresponds to the 15th mēla of the 72 mēla scheme.

2.4 Rāmakalī as seen in SSP:

SSP mentions the lakṣaṇa ślōka given by Vēṅkaṭamakhī for the rāga.

Rāgō rāmakalī gēyā hyārōhē ma ni varjitā |

ṣaḍjagrahā tu sampūrṇā prātaḥ kālēṣu gīyatē ||

Rāmakalī is mentioned as a bhāṣāṅga, sampūrṇa, ṣaḍja graha, rakti, dēśīya raga. Gives the prayōga-s (g g / d p) (d # m / p G) (D p # m G) (d s r G) (# m g d p # m G) (s r g / m G) (d p # m G). Provides the svara contour as below:

Ārōha: sa ri ga pa dha sa

Avarōha: sa ni dha pa ma ga ri sa

The author mentions that it is sampradāya to use prati madhyama in this rāga. People from other regions call this rāga as “Bibhās”. Subbarāma Dīkṣitar has mentioned a gīta of Vēṅkaṭamakhī, a kṛti of Muttuswāmi Dīkṣitar and a sañcāri for which the notations have also been given.

Since it is said to be also called as Bibhās, it is important to look into the evolution of rāga Bibhās too. While sifting the rāga Bibhās, it is observed that there are other two rāga-s namely Vibhāsa and Bibhāsa having similar nomenclature.

3. An overview of the textual references to Bibhāsu:

3.1 Vibhāsa is seen mentioned in the following texts:

1. Rāgamañjari (RM) of Paṇḍarīkaviṭṭala (1572-1578 AD)
2. Saṅgīta Pārijāta (SP) of Ahōbala (17th C.AD)
3. Rāgatattvavibōdha (RTV) of Śrīnīvāsa (after 1650 AD)
4. Hṛdayakautuka (HK) of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 AD)
5. Anūpasanṅītaratnākara (ASR) of Bhāvabhaṭṭa (17th – 18th C.AD)
6. Anūpasanṅītavilāsa of Bhāvabhaṭṭa (ASV), 17th – 18th C. AD

These texts mention Vibhāsa under the 51st mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme of Caturdaṇḍīprakāśikā except for HK and ASR which mention the rāga under 15th mēla.

3.2 Bibhāsa is seen mentioned in the following texts:

1. Rāgamāla (RMala) of Paṇḍarīkaviṭṭala (1576 AD)
2. Hṛdayaparakāśā (HP) of Hṛdayanārāyaṇadēva (1667 AD)

RMala mentions the rāga under the 51st mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme. HP mentions the rāga under the 22nd mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme.

3.3 Bibhāsu is seen mentioned in the following texts:

1. Rāgalakṣaṇamu (RL-S) of Śāhajī, (1684-1711 AD)
2. Saṅgītasārāmṛta of Tulaja (SSA), 1729 – 1735 AD)
3. Rāgalakṣaṇam (RL-MV) of Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī, first quarter of 18th century

RL-S and SSA mention the rāga under the 15th mēla corresponding to the 72 mēla scheme.

3.4 Bibhāsu as seen in RL-S:

Rāga **Bibhāsu** is mentioned as a dēśī rāga under Mālavagauḷa mēla. The rāga is mentioned to be ‘ma’ varja. The svara pattern is given as:

“sa ri ri ga ri sa dha sa ri ga pa dha ni |

ni sa , ni ni dha , pa ga ri pa dha pa dha pa ga ri ri sa |”

There is a mention that the **rāga Rāmakalī** has been used by **Śāhajī in his Tyāgēśa pada-s** in the critical edition and commentary of **Rāgalakṣaṇam of Muddu Vēṅkaṭamakhī**, of **R Sathyanarayana**.

4. Oral Tradition of rāga Rāmakalī as seen in Kārṇāṭaka Music:

The oral tradition pertaining to rāga Rāmakalī is kept up through the kṛti “Rāmarāmakalikalaluśa”. The notation of the kṛti is found in SSP along with the lakṣaṇa. Apart from SSP, T K Govinda Rao in his book “Compositions of Muddusvāmi Dīkṣitar” gives notation to the kṛti.

This part will analyse the compositions in SSP.

4.1 Analysis of Compositions found in SSP:

Subbarāma Dīkṣitar has mentioned a gīta of Vēṅkaṭamakhī, a kṛti of Muttuswāmi Dīkṣitar and a sañcāri for which the notations have also been given.

The pūrvāṅga of the ārōha is 'sa ri ga'

Gīta	Kṛti	Sañcāri
sa ri ga dha (4) Dha sa ri ga Sa ri ga ma ga	Sa ma ga pa	Sa ri ga dha (3) Sa ri ri ga dha dha Ri ga pa dha

The uttarāṅga of the ārōha is 'pa dha sa'

Gīta	Kṛti	Sañcāri
Pa dha sa sa ri ga Ga pa dha sa	Ga pa dha sa sa Ma ga pa dha sa Ri ga pa	Ga pa dha ni (2) Ri ga pa dha sa Ma ga pa dha sa Ga pa dha sa

The pūrvāṅga of the avarōha is 'sa ni dha pa'

Gīta	Kṛti	Sañcāri
Ni dha pa ga Dha pa ma ga Sa ni dha ni dha pa ga	Dha pa ma ga Sa dha pa ma ga Sa ni dha pa ma ga ri ga	Ni dha pa ga Ni dha pa ma ga Sa ni dha pa ma ga ri

The uttarāṅga of the avarōha is ‘ma ga ri sa’

Gīta	Kṛti	Sañcāri
Pa ga ri sa (2)	Dha pa ma ga ri sa (3)	Ga ri ri sa
Sa ri ga ri ga ri sa (2)	Pa ma ga (9)	Pa ma ga ri sa
Sa ri sa ni dha		(3)
		Ri ga ri sa
		Sa ri ga ri sa

The prayōga-s mentioned below are seen frequently in all the three forms:

‘Sa ri ga dha’, ‘Sa ri ga ma ga’, ‘Ga pa dha sa’, ‘Ni dha pa ga’, ‘Dha pa ma ga’, ‘ni dha pa ma ga’, ‘pa ga ri sa’.

The author mentions that it is sampradāya to use prati madhyama in the rāga, but the usage of prati madhyama is not mentioned in the notations. Subbarāma Dīkṣitar in the appendix of SSP, gives the notation for a rāgamālīka of Rāmaswāmi Dīkṣitar. Rāga Rāmakali seems to be one of the rāga-s in the rāgamālīka and at one place there is prati madhyama mentioned in the notation itself. Previously, there was a case where Subbarāma Dīkṣitar, though he has mentioned the usage of prati madhyama in the lakṣaṇa, has not mentioned it in the notation of the kṛti.

The anubandam which contains the rāgamālīka was written by him at a later period. Probably, the author would have realised to mention the prati madhyama in the notation, only while giving the anubandam for SSP.

There are three compositions in the rāga Bibhās found in the text ‘Compositions of Maharaja Śri Swāti Tirunāl in Devanagari and Diacritical Roman Scripts with Notation’ compiled and edited by Saṅgīta Kalānidhi T K Govinda Rao. The list comprises of the following compositions:

1. Mādhavālōkanam – Kucēlōpākhyānam – Ādi
2. Iti Samupāgata – Ajāmiḷōpākhyānam – Mīśra Cāpu
3. Āj Unindē Calē – Hindi Bhajan – Cautāl / Rūpakam

For all the three compositions, the svāra movement is given as under:

Ārōha: sa ri ga pa dha sa

Avarōha: sa dha pa ga ri sa, which is equivalent to the type 1 Bibhās given in RN of Subba Rao. In ‘Balamritham – Swathi Thirunal’ compositions compiled in Malayalam by A S Ranganathayyar gives notation to the above compositions and mentions the rāga Būpālam with antara gāndhāram and hence can be equated to rāga Rēvagupti. Incidentally, rāga Rēvagupti is equivalent to type 1 Bibhās as mentioned by B Subba Rao.

In oral tradition today, there is usage of Prati madhyama prayōga-s. For example, when the phrase P G is sung, P (*m*) G is heard wherein the ‘*m*’ is prati madhyama. Apart from that, the prayōga-s with madhyama which employ **orikkai** as in P m(orikkai) G, the prati ‘ma’ is sung. Whenever there is a combination of orikkai and jāru, the śuddha madhyama is used. The prayōga ‘**g g / d p**’, ‘**D p m g**’, ‘**m g p**’ are frequently seen. The same prayōga-s are seen repetitively in the documented notations too.

5. Oral Tradition of the rāga Rāmkalī in Hindustāni Music:

5.1 Rāmkalī:

B. Subba Rao in Rāga Nidhi (RN) mentions three types of Rāmkalī according to Hindustāni Saṅgīt. All the three types belong to Bhairav thāt.

Type 1: Omits ‘ri’ and ‘ni’ in the ārōha, Jāti is auḍava-sampūrṇa.

Type 2: Omits ‘ri’ in the ārōha, Jāti is śāḍava-sampūrṇa.

Type 3: Sampūrṇa-sampūrṇa

Subba Rao states that Rāmkalī of the South sounds like a combination of Hindustāni rāga-s Bibhās in ārōha and Bhairav in avarōha. He says that it has no resemblance to the Rāmkalī of Hindustāni saṅgīt.

5.2 Bibhās:

B. Subba Rao in RN mentions three types of Bibhās derived from Bhairav thāt, Pūrvi thāt and Mārwa thāt. Bibhās of Bhairav thāt omits ‘ma’ and ‘ni’. Jāti is auḍava-auḍava. Rēvagupti has the same ārōha, avarōha as Bibhās.

Bibhās of Pūrvi thāt (Kāmavardhini) omits ‘ma’ and ‘ni’ in ārōha. Jāti is auḍava-sampūrṇa with tīvra madhyama.

Bibhās of Mārwa thāt (Gamanasrama) is not allied to Rāmkalī in any manner.

In oral tradition today, a frequent use of the phrase ‘p d n ś’ is seen, which is not seen in the South. The phrase ‘s r g m p d n ś’ is used which corresponds to the Rāmkalī mentioned by Subba Rao in his text RN. The usage of ‘s r g m p d n s’ is not seen in the Rāmkalī of South, instead drops both ‘ma’ and ‘ni’ in the ārōha. There is usage of both śuddha and tīvra madhyama as it is seen in the oral tradition of the South.

6. Conclusion:

Through this study, it is seen that rāga Rāmakali of the South has seen some changes. Since none of the texts prior to SSP show traces of Prati madhyama in the rāga Rāmakali, it may be inferred that Rāmakali may have had its roots from rāga Bibhās and gradually the prati madhyama must have crept into the tradition of singing the rāga. This could be one of the reasons why Subbarāma Dīkṣitar did not give the notation of the kṛti with a prati madhyama as it is sung today, though he has mentioned the same in the lakṣaṇa and prayōga-s. But the anubandham section having the rāgamālika contains the prati madhyama which is not seen while discussing the kṛti. This may be because the anubandham was written later by the author.

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